

Assessing ASEAN Centrality in the Contemporary Geopolitical Landscape: A Comparative Perspective with the European Union

In Sophal ☒

*Techo Sen School of Governance and International Relations,
University of Cambodia, Cambodia*

Ro Vannak

*Techo Sen School of Governance and International Relations,
University of Cambodia, Cambodia*

Abstract

With Trump's tariffs meeting its deadline in August 2025, the EU and ASEAN are affected. Given the treatment both entities received from Trump, it has led to the question of how both are relevant on the global stage, and which one is more relevant. This study attempted to tackle this question by analyzing economic data obtained from the official pages of both ASEAN and the EU, and data from the IMF regarding current and projected GDP. Using descriptive statistics with the use of the independent t-test, it was found that ASEAN has strong diplomatic clout and is projected to perform economically better than the EU. This leads to the conclusion that ASEAN is at least as physically, diplomatically, and economically equal to the EU despite its completely different organizational structure.

Keywords: *ASEAN, EU, tariff, Trump, relevance.*

JEL Classification codes: *F36, F53, O19, O53, O57.*

Suggested citation: Sophal, I., & Vannak, R. (2025). Assessing ASEAN Centrality in the Contemporary Geopolitical Landscape: A Comparative Perspective with the European Union. *European Journal of Management, Economics and Business*, 2(4), 150-156. DOI: 10.59324/ejmeb.2025.2(4).12

Introduction

After Donald Trump was inaugurated as President in 2025, he declared tariffs for many nations, through his Executive Order 14257 (2025). Moreover, this has affected allies such as members of the EU, and members of ASEAN. Although he suspended the tariffs for 90 days on April 10, 2025 (Exec. Order. 14,266, 2025), both the EU and ASEAN have been working to resolve the issue and seek a favorable deal before the July 9th deadline (Exec. Order. 14,266, 2025). This has provided the opportunity for several ASEAN member states to negotiate with the US bilaterally such as Indonesia, Vietnam, Brunei, Laos (Medina, 2025) while the current ASEAN Chair, Malaysia, has been aiming for a more united approach (Medina, 2025).

As for the EU, the European Commission is awaiting the response from the US side (Medina, 2025). They have also considered preparing for the case in which an agreement could not be

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

reached (Kerrigan, 2025). Trump’s action can be seen as a test on how ASEAN and the EU are politically and economically relevant on the global stage. Given that both organizations are frequently compared to each other, despite being completely different. However, approaching this question is possible through empirical methods, which is the aim of this paper. In this paper, how ASEAN is relevant compared to the EU globally will be tackled using readily available data.

Materials and Methods

This study attempted to determine the relevance of ASEAN compared to the EU through the use of economical indicators that would reflect ASEAN’s trade capability, and ability to negotiate treaties. The indicator for trade capability and the ability to negotiate treaties involved listing the number of trade partners. Information on this set of data can be obtained from the respective websites of both ASEAN and the EU. Economic data was obtained from the IMF data set. According to the IMF site, statistical estimates and projections were based on data available up until April 14, 2025. In order to understand the context of economic scale, the population size, and land area of ASEAN and EU were obtained from their official websites for comparison.

In the first step, the official website of the EU was accessed and the countries listed to be trade partners were recorded and entered in a table. The list of countries are numbered to show the numbers. The same action was applied for ASEAN. The ASEAN Secretariat website was accessed and the countries that acceded to ASEAN’s Treaty of Amity and Cooperation were listed. These countries were entered into a table and numbered.

To obtain data on GDP growth for both EU and ASEAN, the IMF dashboard was accessed, and an Excel file from the site was downloaded. This file had data from 1980 to 2030 for all countries in the world. Therefore, members of the EU and ASEAN were selected to be analyzed. The analysis included the average GDP growth for EU and ASEAN. This was done by calculating the the average of all the GDP numbers from each country. The standard deviation of the mean for the EU and ASEAN were calculated in order to understand the variance among the countries with both organizations. Furthermore, an independent t-test was used to determine if the difference of averages between the EU and ASEAN were statistically significant. A mathematical comparison of the ASEAN and EU was done by dividing the average of ASEAN over EU:

ASEAN/EU, where a value lower than 1 means that the EU outperformed ASEAN, and a number greater than 1 means that ASEAN had better performance.

Data regarding the land size and population of both EU and ASEAN does not require the calculation above, as the results would seem obvious.

Based on the steps described above, the results regarding EU and ASEAN trade partners were as follows:

Table 1. Countries that Trade with EU by Continents and Regions

Africa	Asia	Europe	The Middle East	America	Oceania
1. Algeria	5. Azerbaijan	24. Armenia	35. Iran	40. Brazil	46. Australia
2. Egypt	6. Bangladesh	25. Belarus	36. Iraq	41. Canada	New Zealand
3. Libya	7. Cambodia	26. Faroe Islands	37. Israel	42. Chile	
4. Morocco	8. China	27. Georgia	38. Jordan	43. Mexico	
South Africa	9. Hong Kong SAR	28. Iceland	39. Lebanon	44. Paraguay	
	10. India	29. Moldova	Palestine.	45. the United States	

	11. Indonesia 12. Japan 13. Kazakhstan 14. Laos 15. Malaysia 16. Myanmar 17. Pakistan 18. the Philippines 19. Singapore 20. South Korea 21. Sri Lanka 22. Taiwan 23. Thailand Vietnam	30. Norway 31. Russia 32. Switzerland 33. Turkiye 34. Ukraine the United Kingdom		Venezuela	
--	--	---	--	-----------	--

Source: European Commission (2024)

Table 2. Countries that Trade and Entered the Treaty of Amity and Cooperation with ASEAN

Africa	Asia	Europe	The Middle East	America	Oceania
1. Egypt 2. Morocco South Africa	3. Bangladesh 4. <u>China</u> 5. East Timor 6. India 7. <u>Japan</u> 8. Kazakhstan 9. Mongolia 10. North Korea 11. Pakistan 12. <u>South Korea</u> 13. Sri Lanka	14. Denmark 15. France 16. Germany 17. Greece 18. Netherlands 19. Norway 20. Russia 21. Serbia 22. Spain 23. the UK 24. Turkiye Ukraine	25. Bahrain 26. Iran 27. Kuwait 28. Oman 29. Qatar 30. Saudi Arabia 31. UAE	32. Argentina 33. Canada 34. Chile 35. Columbia 36. Cuba 37. Panama 38. Peru 39. the US 40. Brazil	41. <u>Australia</u> 42. <u>New Zealand</u> 43. Papua New Guinea

Source: ASEAN Secretariat (2024)

Table 3. Real GDP Growth (Annual percent change) of ASEAN and the EU

	Region	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Brunei Darussalam	ASEAN	1.1	-1.6	-1.6	1.4	3.9	2.5	2.6	2.6	2.9	3.1	3
Cambodia	ASEAN	-3.6	3.1	5.1	5	6	4	3.4	4.3	5	5.1	5.2
Indonesia	ASEAN	-2.1	3.7	5.3	5	5	4.7	4.7	4.9	5	5.1	5.1
Lao P.D.R.	ASEAN	-0.4	2.1	2.3	3.7	4.3	2.5	2	2	2	2	2
Malaysia	ASEAN	-5.5	3.3	8.9	3.6	5.1	4.1	3.8	4	4	4	4
Myanmar	ASEAN	-9	-12	4	1	-1.1	1.9	2.1	2	1.8	1.8	1.8
Philippines	ASEAN	-9.5	5.7	7.6	5.5	5.7	5.5	5.8	6.1	6.2	6.3	6.3
Singapore	ASEAN	-3.8	9.8	4.1	1.8	4.4	2	1.9	2.3	2.5	2.5	2.5
Thailand	ASEAN	-6.1	1.5	2.6	2	2.5	1.8	1.6	1.9	2.1	2.3	2.4
Vietnam	ASEAN	2.9	2.6	8.5	5.1	7.1	5.2	4	5.2	5.3	5.3	5.3

Austria	EU	-6.3	4.8	5.3	-1	-1.2	-0.3	0.8	1.6	1.2	1.1	0.9
Belgium	EU	-4.8	6.2	4.2	1.3	1	0.8	1	1.2	1.3	1.3	1.3
Bulgaria	EU	-3.2	7.8	4	1.9	2.8	2.5	2.7	2.7	2.6	2.5	2.5
Croatia	EU	-8.3	12.6	7.3	3.3	3.8	3.1	2.7	2.6	2.6	2.5	2.5
Cyprus	EU	-3.2	11.4	7.4	2.6	3.4	2.5	2.7	3	3	3	3
Czech Republic	EU	-5.3	4	2.8	-0.1	1.1	1.6	1.8	1.9	2	2	2
Denmark	EU	-1.8	7.4	1.5	2.5	3.7	2.9	1.8	1.6	1.5	1.5	1.4
Estonia	EU	-2.9	7.2	0.1	-3	-0.3	0.7	1.8	1.8	1.9	1.8	1.7
Finland	EU	-2.5	2.7	0.8	-0.9	-0.1	1	1.4	1.4	1.3	1.2	1.2
France	EU	-7.6	6.8	2.6	1.1	1.1	0.6	1	1.2	1.3	1.2	1.2
Germany	EU	-4.1	3.7	1.4	-0.3	-0.2	0	0.9	1.5	1.2	1	0.7
Greece	EU	-9.2	8.7	5.7	2.3	2.3	2	1.8	1.3	1.5	1.4	1.4
Hungary	EU	-4.3	7.2	4.3	-0.8	0.5	1.4	2.6	2.8	3	3	3
Ireland	EU	7.2	16.3	8.6	-5.5	1.2	2.3	2.1	2.1	2.2	2.2	2.3
Italy	EU	-8.9	8.9	4.8	0.7	0.7	0.4	0.8	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.7
Latvia	EU	-3.5	6.9	1.8	2.9	-0.4	2	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
Lithuania	EU	0	6.4	2.5	0.4	2.7	2.8	2.5	2.5	2.4	2.4	2.4
Luxembourg	EU	-0.5	6.9	-1.1	-0.7	1	1.6	2.2	2.3	2.2	2.1	2.1
Malta	EU	-3.4	13.3	4.3	6.8	6	3.9	3.9	4	4	4	4
Netherlands	EU	-3.9	6.3	5	0.1	1	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.3	1.2
Poland	EU	-2	6.9	5.3	0.1	2.9	3.2	3.1	3	2.9	2.8	2.7
Portugal	EU	-8.2	5.6	7	2.6	1.9	2	1.7	1.5	1.7	1.6	1.7
Romania	EU	-3.7	5.5	4	2.4	0.9	1.6	2.8	3.2	3.3	3.4	3.5
Slovak Republic	EU	-2.6	5.7	0.4	1.4	2	1.3	1.7	2.5	2.5	2.2	2.1
Slovenia	EU	-4.1	8.4	2.7	2.1	1.6	1.8	2.4	2.5	2.4	2.3	2.3
Spain	EU	-10.9	6.7	6.2	2.7	3.2	2.5	1.8	1.7	1.6	1.6	1.6
Sweden	EU	-2	5.9	1.5	-0.1	1	1.9	2.2	1.9	1.7	1.7	1.7

Source: IMF (2025)

Table 3. Land Area and Population

Organization and source	Population (million)	Land Area (million square miles)
EU (Eurostat, 2025)	450.4	4
ASEAN (ASEAN Stats, 2025)	677.6	4.5

Source: Eurostat (2025), ASEAN Stats (2025)

Results

Comparison Between EU and ASEAN

Number of trade partners:

According to the official numbers of partners of ASEAN and the EU, the results were as follow:

- ASEAN Trade partners = 45, including EU 27
- EU Trade partners = 52

It should be noted that ASEAN has increased cooperation with some TAC signatories. First, ASEAN led discussions on the Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership (RCEP). These non-ASEAN signatories of the RCEP include China, Japan, South Korea, Australia, and New Zealand. More recently, it met with the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) to increase trade in May 2025. The GCC members have already acceded to the TAC and they include Bahrain, Kuwait, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, and UAE.

Growth and projected growth

For convenience, GDP growth was divided into two parts. The first part was from 2020 to 2025. The second part was from 2026 to 2030. This period would be projections made by the IMF.

Table 4. Analysis of ASEAN and EU GDP

	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Average ASEAN	-3.600	1.820	4.680	3.410	4.290	3.420
Average EU	-4.074	7.415	3.719	0.919	1.615	1.759
Standard deviation of ASEAN	4.092	5.672	3.192	1.727	2.270	1.437
Standard deviation of EU	3.559	2.997	2.475	2.293	1.589	1.013
T-test	0.732	0.000	0.339	0.004	0.000	0.000
ASEAN/EU	0.884	0.245	1.259	3.713	2.657	1.944

The analysis indicates that ASEAN outperformed the EU from 2020 to 2025 in general, with the exception of the year 2021. The difference between ASEAN and the EU on that particular year was statistically significant, as the p-value of the T-test was 0. In that year, ASEAN's GDP was less than 25 percent that of the EU. The following year saw no statistically significant difference between the GDP of the EU and ASEAN, however, starting from 2023 to 2025, the trend reversed and ASEAN performed significantly better. In 2023, ASEAN performed almost quadruple the GDP of the EU. In 2024, ASEAN's GDP amounted to more than twice that of the EU. In 2025, ASEAN's GDP was still significantly higher than the EU.

Table 5. Analysis of ASEAN and EU GDP Projection

	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Average ASEAN	3.190	3.530	3.680	3.750	3.760
Average EU	2.004	2.085	2.070	2.011	1.985
T-test	0.002	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000
Standard deviation of ASEAN	1.387	1.556	1.613	1.618	1.623
Standard deviation of EU	0.765	0.766	0.775	0.797	0.832
ASEAN/EU	1.592	1.693	1.777	1.865	1.894

Based on IMF estimates, ASEAN is projected to outperform the EU by a statistically significant margin. From 2026 to 2030, ASEAN is expected to have a GDP growth rate between 3 to around 4 while the EU is expected to be around 2 in the same period.

Discussion

In the current situation, it can be seen that ASEAN is a comparable economic power to the EU. In terms of physical land area, and population, it is larger. It has comparable reach diplomatically. Though it had slightly less trade partners with the EU, it managed to successfully conclude the RCEP, and this year increased economic cooperation with the GCC. Though the GCC had entered the Treaty of Amity with ASEANs, its meeting for more economic cooperation with ASEAN happens to be in the same year as Trump's tariffs. The RCEP negotiations, on the other hand, started in 2013 but concluded in 2020, according to the ASEAN official website. The final years of the negotiations also coincided with Trump's first term. The timing indicates that in response to both Trump terms, ASEAN is relevant to other parties too. This indicates ASEAN's relevance in the political stage since it is considered a mega-regional trade agreement, and the only other comparable agreement in scale is the Comprehensive and Progressive Agreement for Trans-Pacific Partnership (CPTPP) (European Parliament, 2021). It is seen as a political win for ASEAN in its role as a middle-power (European Parliament, 2021). With regards to ASEAN's GDP growth compared to the EU, the IMF data shows that ASEAN is projected to continue its growth and outperform the EU. Given that Trump's impending tariff deadline would end in August and affect both the EU and ASEAN, it cannot be denied that ASEAN remains relevant in the global economy.

The results of the study employed quantitative data to measure the relevance of ASEAN compared to the EU. This approach is simple and provides useful tools to analyze political relevance in the context of economy. This approach is already done with military power, where the budget allocated to defense, the number of active military personnel, etc are clearly shown and compared on a dashboard. However, a multi-faceted approach to analyzing two entities such as the EU and ASEAN has not been widely done. The approach to analyzing political relevance is simple, practical, and can provide an unbiased evaluation of the performance of both the EU and ASEAN. Further research can be done on the performance of other groupings such as the GCC, or MERCOSUR. It also provides a basis for political calculation in order to leverage and bargain with larger countries.

Conclusion

To conclude, ASEAN and the EU are two important global actors. As a region, both groupings have similar land size and population size. Diplomatically, both have their own unique strength. The EU, functioning as a supranational entity, can use its integrated market to attract investors and trade. ASEAN, an association of governments, can use its diplomatic skills to create more cooperation among different regions and powers. Given that it has a similar land area to the EU, it needs to physically integrate in order to capitalize on more gains and relevance. Currently, with its structure, it managed to engage different regions and negotiate the largest trade agreement and contributed in writing the rules of the world. This is a clear demonstration that ASEAN is very relevant, and still has room for improvement in order to be more relevant on the global stage.

Acknowledgement

I would like to thank my co-writer Ro Vannak, who suggested the topic and was immensely helpful in this research. All the materials were obtained from free from reputable sources without any contribution that would lead to any conflict of interest.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- ASEAN Stats. (2025). *ASEAN Statistical Highlights 2024*. <https://www.aseanstats.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/ASH-2024-v1-1.pdf>
- ASEAN Stats. (2025, May 15). ASEANStatsDataPortal: Indicators. Retrieved July 15, 2025, from <https://data.aseanstats.org/>
- Calfee, R. C., & Valencia, R. R. (1991). *APA guide to preparing manuscripts for journal publication*. Washington, DC: American Psychological Association.
- EU trade relations with Association of South East Asian Nations (ASEAN). (n.d.). *EU Trade*. Retrieved July 7, 2025, from https://policy.trade.ec.europa.eu/eu-trade-relationships-country-and-region/countries-and-regions/association-south-east-asian-nations-asean_en
- European Commission. (n.d.). *EU trade relations with China*. Retrieved July 12, 2025, from https://policy.trade.ec.europa.eu/eu-trade-relationships-country-and-region/countries-and-regions/china_en
- European Parliament. (2021). *Short overview of the Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership (RCEP)* (Briefing 10-02-2021). Brussels, Belgium: European Parliament. https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document.html?reference=EXPO_BRI%282021%29653625
- European Union. (2025). *Key facts and figures*. Retrieved July 15, 2025, from https://european-union.europa.eu/principles-countries-history/facts-and-figures-european-union_en
- Eurostat. (2025, July 11). *EU population increases for the 4th consecutive year*. European Commission. Retrieved July 15, 2025, from <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/w/ddn-20250711-1>
- Kerrigan, A. (2025, June 27). EU leaders mull new US trade proposals ahead of Trump tariffs deadline. *France24*. Retrieved June 27, 2025, from <https://www.france24.com/en/europe/20250627-eu-leaders-mull-new-us-trade-proposals-ahead-of-trump-tariffs-deadline>
- Medina, A. F. (2025, April 10). ASEAN's unified response to U.S. tariffs. *ASEAN Briefing*. <http://www.aseanbriefing.com/news/aseans-response-to-u-s-tariffs-toward-a-unified-regional-strategy/>
- The White House. (2025, April 15). *Executive Order 14266* (Vol. 90, Issue 71) [Presidential executive order]. <https://www.whitehouse.gov/>
- The White House. (2025, April 2). *Executive Order 14257* [Presidential executive order]. <https://www.whitehouse.gov/>
- Verhelst, K. (2025, July 11). EU to Trump on tariffs: The ball is in your court. *Politico*. Retrieved July 12, 2025, from <https://www.politico.eu/article/eu-donald-trump-tariffs-deal-trade-10-percent/>

